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Executive summary

This case study examines the 2022 Austrian Eco-Social Tax Reform (*Eco-Social Tax Reform Act 2022 (Ökosoziales Steuerreformgesetz 2022)*) focusing on its policy drivers, design process, implementation dynamics, and distributional implications of the policy mechanism. The reform introduced a national carbon price alongside a broader tax package that reduced labour and corporate taxation and increased targeted tax credits. A central component was the Klimabonus, a per-capita transfer intended to compensate households for higher energy prices resulting from the CO₂ levy. In simple terms, while the reform aimed to internalise the cost of emissions by making polluters pay and thereby incentivising more sustainable behaviour, the Klimabonus was designed to offset these costs, ensuring that lower-emitting households would not disproportionately bear the burden of others' emissions.

The introduction of carbon pricing in Austria reflected longstanding pressure from climate economists and environmental policy experts on the Government as they advocated for the internalisation of carbon externalities, i.e. the unintended costs caused by carbon emissions (CO₂) that are not paid by the emitter but by society as a whole. The Greens entered government in 2020 with carbon pricing as one of their core programme commitments. Based on policy proponent of the reform, it is suggested that this measure might have been prioritised to align Austrian climate policy with scientific recommendations and to address persistent stagnation in emission reduction, especially in transport, that Austria had recorded. The conservative coalition partner of Greens agreed to adopt the measure as part of the negotiated government programme, although it did not originate from its electoral platform.

The reform was developed in a context of stable parliamentary majorities and strong party discipline. Given the political set-up in Austria, i.e. decision-making power tends to be concentrated within the executive branch and party leadership, there was limited intra-parliamentary contestation of the reform. The tax reform appeared on the policy agenda largely because of the coalition negotiations rather than external social and civil mobilisation. The parliamentary debate showed clear political polarisation: the governing parties supported the reform as an economic and ecological modernisation (Greens), while opposition parties criticised it on grounds ranging from distributional concerns (SPÖ) to perceived cost burdens and administrative complexity (FPÖ, NEOS).

The CO₂ price and Klimabonus were designed jointly to ensure compensatory neutrality. However, it appears that the link between the tax and the bonus was poorly understood by the public, which contributed to perceptions of unfairness of the reform. The 2022–2023 energy crisis further complicated attribution effects, making it difficult for citizens to disentangle market-driven price increases from the carbon levy. The reform was adopted in Parliament solely with the votes of the governing coalition, limiting political ownership across parties. A subsequent change in government in years 2023-2024 led to the weakening of the

Klimabonus while retaining the CO₂ price, thereby removing the primary distributional balancing mechanism and shifting the negative distributional effects on the low-income population.

The analysis highlighted central distributional challenge: carbon taxes are regressive, where the policy imposes a proportionally higher burden on lower-income households than on higher-income ones, unless accompanied by adequate compensation. The initial per-capita Klimabonus compensated poorer households more strongly in relative terms. With its removal, the remaining CO₂ levy appeared to have a clearer regressive profile, with disproportionate negative effect on low-income households, renters, and urban dwellers reliant on gas heating.

Overall, the Austrian case demonstrates how policy design and implementation structures, rather than the carbon price itself, can generate or mitigate inequalities. It also shows how limited stakeholder engagement and lack of clear public communication, fragmented political support, and insufficient monitoring can weaken the perceived legitimacy of transition-related measures.

1 Introduction

1.1 Austria's efforts to reduce emissions

It is well established that governments must undertake action to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Due to a rapid and often unregulated urbanization, there is an intensified air pollution posing serious risks to health and the environment. As urban populations grow, air quality has become a critical concern worldwide [R20]. To this aim, according to the European Environmental Agency (EEA), Austria has made progress in terms of “comprehensive transformation” excelling mostly in organic farming and renewable energy [R21].

To reduce the effects of climate change, GHG must be lowered (including carbon dioxide (CO₂)) requiring unilateral and national actions, such as national carbon taxes to stabilise and reduce human-made emissions and favour renewable energy [R23]. Carbon taxes tackle an economic problem as they target the behavioural changes of individuals and industrial actors factoring in the social costs of global warming [R24].

BOX 1 From EU to Austria: environmental objectives to reduce GHG Emissions

Austria aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2040, ten years ahead of the EU target. Between 2005 and 2023, it reduced GHG emissions by 25%, below the EU average of 30%, with most reductions coming from sectors covered by the emissions trading system. While Austria met its 2020 effort-sharing targets, further action is needed to meet 2030 commitments. The carbon sink capacity of land use (LULUCF) has also declined in recent years. After delays and infringement procedures, Austria submitted an updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) in 2024. The country allocates 56% of its €4 billion recovery plan to climate action. Public awareness is relatively high, with nearly half of Austrians considering climate change among the most serious global issues [R27].

As presented in Box 1, at European level Austria has been performing well at reducing GHG emissions. Austria's Climate Change Act (2011), the founding policy document guiding climate action, did not initially include targets beyond 2020. While the long-term strategy originally set climate neutrality for 2050, the 2020 government programme advanced this target to 2040. Austria met several 2020 EU targets, though partly influenced by reduced activity during COVID-19 and narrowly missed its final energy consumption goal. Emissions have declined significantly since 2005, but remain slightly above the EU average, and further reductions, especially in transport, are needed to meet 2030 and 2040 targets [R27]. Austria's emissions have been decreasing (Figure 1) but remain above global and EU averages.

Figure 1 CO₂ per capita emissions for Austria compared to EU27 and Global (sum of all countries measured); Source: [R28] own production (2026)

Austria has introduced several initiatives to support decarbonisation, investments in renewable energy expansion, and measures to promote sustainable mobility. These include subsidies for electric vehicles and significant funding for public transport infrastructure [R29]. The country also allocates a substantial share of its recovery and resilience resources—over half of the total—to climate-related objectives, with a particular focus on clean transport and renewable energy under the REPowerEU Framework. At the same time, delays in submitting and finalising the updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), which led to infringement procedures at EU level, illustrate governance and coordination challenges within the policy process [R27].

From an institutional perspective, Austria's climate governance is characterised by a combination of formal structures and limited enforcement capacity. While bodies such as the National Climate Protection Committee and the Climate Citizens' Council have been established to support policy development and stakeholder engagement, their influence on actual policy outcomes appears constrained. In 2021, national data research collected showed the need to better coordinate climate policies [R30]. Similarly, although Austria is recognised for the use of green budgeting instruments and has been praised for introducing the Eco-Social tax reform as a shift towards integrating environmental objectives into fiscal policy, important shortcomings remain [R27]. These include continued fossil fuel subsidies, insufficient progress in phasing out oil and gas heating systems, and gaps in energy efficiency legislation. As reflected in international assessments, Austria's overall climate policy

performance is therefore considered moderate, highlighting the gap between stated ambitions and effective implementation.

This broader context is crucial for understanding the Eco-Social Tax reform. The reform emerges within a policy environment where ambitious climate targets coexist with structural constraints, institutional fragmentation, and uneven sectoral progress. As such, it provides a particularly relevant case to analyse how fiscal instruments are used to address climate objectives, and how their design and implementation interact with existing economic structures and social inequalities.

The reform predates Austria's new government, which took office in 2025 and declined to endorse the European Commission's recommendation of a 90% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2040 [R31].

1.2 Austria's National Carbon Tax

Considering the Austria's efforts to reduce emissions, EU institutions recognise Austria's Eco-Social tax reform as a positive step in shifting the tax burden and reducing emissions, alongside strong green budgeting practices. However, Austria's overall climate policy performance is marked by persistent fossil fuel subsidies, limited progress in phasing out gas and oil heating, and an outdated climate framework.

To balance environmental and social needs, Austria sets a useful example with the *Eco-Social Tax Reform Act (Ökosoziales Steuerreformgesetz 2022, hereby Eco-Soc Tax)*, introduced in 2022 which marks the country's first comprehensive attempt to align fiscal policy with climate objectives while addressing social equity concerns [R1] [R22]. At its core, the reform established a national carbon pricing system, applied primarily to fossil fuels used in transport and heating in households and industry. The carbon levy was initially set at €30 per ton of CO₂, with a planned trajectory that would gradually increase the rate to €55 by 2025 [R2]. Starting 2026, this national pricing is scheduled to be replaced by/integrated into a new EU-wide emission trading system for transportation and buildings (see below on EU ETS) [R25].

The rationale behind this measure was twofold: first, to create a clear price signal that would incentivise households and businesses to reduce carbon-intensive consumption and accelerate the transition towards cleaner energy sources; second, to do so in a socially balanced manner. To offset the additional burden on citizens, especially those with lower or middle incomes, the government introduced a climate bonus (*Klimabonus*). Revenues from this carbon levy were going to be redistributed through a geographically adjusted lump-sum transfer, designed to offset regressive effects by decoupling compensation from individual emissions; however, its removal transformed the mechanism into a net regressive tax.

Complementing the carbon price and the climate bonus, the reform also included broader tax relief measures. These involved reductions in income taxes and social security contributions,

with the explicit aim of strengthening purchasing power and making the reform more politically acceptable. Taken together, the Eco-Soc Tax reform sought to demonstrate that climate action and social fairness could be pursued simultaneously, positioning Austria as an early mover within the European Union in embedding distributive justice into carbon pricing.

This Tax is complementary to the Austrian National emission trading scheme [R3] applied in 2022. The trading scheme's aim was to go beyond the European Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) [R4]. The referenced document is an official draft legislative proposal (*Begutachtungsentwurf*) published through the Austrian legal information system (RIS), providing detailed insight into the legal structure, implementation mechanisms, and policy rationale of the national carbon pricing system [R19]. Launched in 2005, EU ETS requires polluters to pay for their GHGs covering electricity and heat generation, industrial manufacturing, and aviation sectors operating in all EU Member States [R3]. Under this system companies must monitor emissions yearly.

Austria has its own National Emissions Trading Act 2022 system *Nationales Emissionszertifikatehandelsgesetz* (NEHG 2022) (Box 2). NEHG provided a national carbon-pricing system for emissions not covered by EU ETS I, with later integration into EU ETS II. The system was launched on 1 October 2022 and was designed in two phases: an introductory fixed-price phase and a later transition phase. The certificate price started at €30 per tonne of CO₂ in 2022, rose to €32.5 in 2023 after a price-stability adjustment, then to €45 in 2024 and €55 in 2025. Legally, the obligation falls on the entities placing fuels on the market, but the cost is transmitted downstream through higher fuel and heating prices [R33].

BOX 2 Austria's own ETS System (Nationales Emissionszertifikatehandelsgesetz) [R32]

The following law establishes Austria's national emissions pricing system for GHG in sectors not covered by the EU ETS I, with the explicit aim of later integrating it into EU ETS II (2026). The main objectives are:

- reduce greenhouse gas emissions outside the EU ETS I,
- contribute to Austria's Paris Agreement and EU climate obligations,
- prepare integration into the EU ETS II from 2027 onward.

This law also establishes monitoring instructions to the trading participants (ie. companies).

The Eco-Soc Tax was politically prepared in the context of the 2020 government programme, when the ÖVP–Greens coalition brought together two priorities: stronger climate action and broader fiscal reform. In practical terms, the package combined tax relief measures with a new carbon-pricing instrument for sectors outside the classic EU ETS, especially transport and heating. The parliamentary process then moved in late 2021 and early 2022 through two

linked legal tracks: the Eco-Social Tax Reform Act 2022 Part I [R34], which included the national emissions pricing framework, and the Klimabonus Act [R35], which created the compensation mechanism for residents. The National Council approved the reform package in January 2022, and the *Bundesrat*¹ cleared it in February 2022.

The case study reviews the reform's policy design and implementation, underlying the complexity of calculating and reducing emissions laying responsibility of those who pollute without affecting other actors. The Eco-Soc Tax remains a relevant empirical case to show how actions can translate into concrete distributional outcomes that aim to balance environmental effectiveness and social equity.

It should be noted that academic analysis of the Eco-Soc tax reform in Austria is not available, based on the results of the research we performed in Scopus (in December 2025) and other similar sources. The analysis therefore draws on desk research across non-academic literature and interviews performed for this case.

The elements presented in this introduction provide an overview of Austria's climate policy landscape. In this context, the Eco-Social Tax Reform— and in particular the introduction of a national emissions pricing system alongside the Klimabonus— offers a critical case through which to examine **how climate policy instruments are translated into practice**. The reform is especially relevant as it combines environmental objectives with explicit redistributive mechanisms, while also revealing the fragility of such balances over time.

¹ The *Bundesrat* is the second chamber of the Austrian Parliament, composed of representatives of the federal states, which participates in the legislative process by reviewing and approving laws passed by the National Council.

2 The Eco-Soc Tax policy process

The Eco-Soc Tax aims as a fiscal package to reduce GHG and “ecologise” the domestic tax [R5], while reducing the tax burden on households and businesses. This reform proposed to incentivise pro-green behaviour while reducing GHG and allow financing in favour of social causes. The reform was approved post-covid leading to parliamentary tensions.

The Eco-Soc Tax complements the EU ETS that is focused on companies. The EU ETS is based on a “cap and trade” system where the cap defines the limit on the total amount of GHG that can emitted based on EU standards refined annually with EU climate policies [R25]. Within the ETS, each company gets an allowance (where 1 allowance = one tonne of CO₂) which is reduced every year. Companies can buy or receive allowances distributed at auctions regulated per Member State [R26], where quantity required increases proportionally with their level of emissions. Hence, either these companies trade allowances or pay a large fine.

The underlying logic focused on trade aims to incentivise companies to emit less or pay more. Since 2013, these payments totalled over 175 billion EUR and served EU Member States to invest into renewable energy or low carbon technologies. The revenues from ETS fund EU programs such as the Innovation Fund or the Modernisation Fund. The EU ETS’s legislative framework is spelled out in the ETS Directive that draws on the European Green New Deal, European Climate Law, and the Fit for 55 [R25].

To balance the auction of these allowances, the EU created the Market Stability Reserve (MSR) [R7] agreed in 2015 as a solution to the surplus of allowances. The need for creation of MSR was set out by the number of unused allowances resulting from lower expected emissions and cheaper international credits (and the 2008 economic crisis). In simple terms, this reserve corrects the allowances available at auction adjusting the overall available cap.

Table 1 Stakeholders Involved

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
Public	Civil Society (unspecified) (i.e. households)	This stakeholder relates to all those that are not companies or businesses. They are divided by the reform by geographical location and socioeconomic status.
Private	Companies / Businesses	This stakeholder relates to companies and their own emissions within the country.
Government / State	Policy-Makers	Central and multifaceted role as regulator, redistributor, and coordinator of the transition.

2.1 Political and Institutional Dynamics

The Eco Soc Tax Reform was passed with a coalition composed of centre-right parties People's Party (ÖVP) and the Greens, opposed by the centre-left Social Democratic Party (SPÖ), the right-wing Freedom Party (FPÖ), and the free-market New Austrians (NEOS).

Table 2 is relevant highlighting the political positioning of key actors and clarifies the distribution of support and opposition surrounding the reform. By mapping party stances and underlying motivations, the table illustrates that the Eco-Social Tax Reform was not the outcome of broad political consensus, but rather the **result of coalition dynamics within a relatively centralised decision-making system**.

Table 2 Party / Politician Positioning Related to the Reform [R8]

Party	Role	Reason
SPÖ	Opposed (partial support)	Partial support regarding the taxes on labour but does not agree on the low tax burden on capital and wealth, supporting the idea that this tax will help (rich) companies.
FPÖ	Opposed	Described it as an unfair CO ₂ tax and distributed unevenly burdening on citizens.
NEOS	Opposed (partial support)	Supportive what regards greening the fiscal system, however, does not believe it would achieve climate goals.
ÖVP	Proponent	Found that the opposition did not understand the reform, describing it as "climate protection with common sense."
Greens	Proponent	Described it as a revolution in the tax system, where climate-damaging behaviour is given a price tag.
Magnus Brunner ² (former Austrian Finance Minister until 2024. He is currently European Commissioner for Internal Affairs and Migration)	Supporter	Found the reform would generate capital, create additional jobs, and reduce the tax burden.
Werner Kogler (former Green Leader and Minister of Culture until 2025 and Vice Chancellor until 2024. Currently no role)	Supporter	Described it as a milestone, where fluctuations of prices (ie. energy) can be adjusted and provide a reliable path.

The political parties raised concerns about the distributional consequences of carbon pricing, pointing to risks of regressive effects on lower-income households. In practice, this referred to cases such as poorer households devoting a larger share of their income to heating and mobility, rural and peripheral residents with limited transport alternatives, renters who

² A name of a politician is provided and not a party whenever this detail is provided in the original source.

cannot directly invest in cleaner heating technologies, and gas-dependent households facing increased energy costs without adequate short-term adjustment options. These two concerns, i.e., environmental effectiveness and social justice, defined the problem to be addressed at the Parliamentary level.

The reform entered the political agenda in the early 2020s, a period characterised by heightened public awareness of climate change and strengthened EU commitments to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. Domestically, the coalition government formed by the Austrian People's Party (ÖVP) and the Greens provided the political space to translate the long-discussed idea of an Eco-Social Tax into concrete policy. The Greens had explicitly campaigned for a carbon price linked to redistribution, while the ÖVP emphasised tax relief and economic competitiveness. The alignment of these priorities enabled the reform to be prioritised in the coalition programme and fast-tracked in 2021–2022.

The design phase placed emphasis on **balancing ecological effectiveness with social inclusiveness**. The government established the CO₂ levy with a predictable price path, thereby providing certainty to firms and households, while simultaneously introducing the Klimabonus, a universal transfer to citizens financed through carbon revenues. Stakeholder engagement was mentioned as present in parliamentary debates and consultations with industry associations, trade unions, and consumer organisations. Civil society groups contributed by pressing for fairness considerations, while business lobbies argued for transitional support measures to preserve competitiveness. This inclusive design aimed to mitigate social opposition and enhance legitimacy.

Implementation was assigned to national ministries and relevant tax authorities, with the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Climate Action taking leading roles. The reform's execution encountered challenges, notably in the context of soaring energy prices following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022. The latter unforeseen development led the government to postpone the planned increase in the carbon levy (from €30 per tonne in 2022 to €35 in 2023), in order to mitigate additional cost-of-living pressures during the energy crisis.

The monitoring of the Eco-Social Tax reform is primarily embedded in the National Emissions Trading Act 2022 (NEHG 2022), which establishes a structured administrative system for tracking implementation and compliance. Under the reform, trading participants placing covered fossil fuels on the market must register with the competent authority, submit a monitoring plan, calculate the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the fuels they market, and report these emissions annually through an official emissions report. These reports must be verified by an independent accredited body, while the competent authority—Austria's Customs Office, through the dedicated office for national emissions certificate trading—can review, correct, or estimate emissions where data are missing or inaccurate. Monitoring therefore relies on measurable fuel quantities, standardised emission factors, annual reporting obligations, certificate surrender requirements, and enforcement

mechanisms for non-compliance. While this provides a relatively detailed framework for technical and administrative monitoring, the reform itself appears less explicit in institutionalising the monitoring of its broader social and distributional effects.

As shown by Figure 3 overall environmental taxes have increased. The unit is defined as taxes whose tax base has a negative impact on the environment [R38]. While they might not be directly descriptive of behaviour, these results are indicative of which sectors need to be given more attention (i.e. transport and energy).

Figure 2. Austria's Environmental Taxes (Updated 2026); Source: [R38] own production

Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms were formally embedded in the reform. Key performance indicators centred on emission reductions in the targeted sectors, household-level redistribution through the climate bonus, and fiscal neutrality. While comprehensive impact evaluations are still at an early stage, initial assessments suggest that the **climate bonus has been effective in cushioning households against higher fuel costs**, although questions remain about the adequacy of compensation for rural households with limited low carbon mobility options, such as reliable public transport, cycling infrastructure, shared mobility services, or access to electric vehicles and charging points. Data quality and transparency are generally high in Austrian policy system, reflecting Austria's established statistical capacity, yet the long-term effectiveness of the reform in shifting behavioural patterns will only become visible as the carbon price trajectory progresses.

2.2 Austria's Social Dynamics

Klimabonus's weakening is a relevant topic to present alongside the reform, since it was initially inserted to avoid imbalance at whom would be paying the cost of emissions. As Figure 3 shows social vulnerability (measured in persons at risk of poverty and social exclusion) in Austria is relatively contained but persistent and structurally stable, not disappearing although if doing better than EU's average.

Figure 3. Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion; Source: [R36] own production

As the next section will present with inputs from one of the reform's proponents from the Austrian Green Party, social acceptance was necessary from the public as well as from the opposing political parties. Social acceptance can increase if the tax burden from climate policies is distributed fairly and the funds raised are used effectively [R37]. However, as the interviewee specifies, adequate and strong communication is needed, and for the Austria's case, it was weak resulting in the abolition of Klimabonus. More generally carbon taxes are accepted, including measures to mitigate emissions and provide alternative for heating and transportation (rural especially) [R37]. Education emerges as the strongest and most consistent predictor of acceptance, while frequent car use is associated with lower support, especially for mobility-related measures. Rural residence matters less once car dependence is taken into account, suggesting that **perceived personal cost and limited alternatives** are central to explaining resistance. These findings are highly relevant for the Austrian reform: they indicate that the political sustainability of carbon pricing depends not only on abstract support for climate action, but also on whether affected groups perceive the policy as fair, understandable, and compatible with their everyday constraints.

Support and Objection of the policies in comparison
(according to the share of respondents, without the categories 'neither nor/don't know')

Figure 4. Austrian's social acceptance to climate policies; Source and production: [R37]

In this respect, the Klimabonus can be understood as a key mechanism for sustaining legitimacy: it addressed the distributive concerns typically associated with carbon pricing by recycling revenues back to residents through a visible compensation instrument

BOX 3 Austria's Social Welfare [R38]

Austria's social inclusion framework is grounded in a comparatively strong welfare state, which provides broad access to healthcare, education, family support, and targeted services for vulnerable groups. This institutional setting helps reduce inequality and social exclusion, including among children and young people. At the same time, recent economic pressures, such as inflation, labour market insecurity, housing costs, and climate-related challenges, have increased vulnerability, particularly for disadvantaged groups. Social exclusion risks are higher where multiple forms of disadvantage overlap, including disability, migrant background, unstable family conditions, or limited educational attainment. Available evidence shows that, despite extensive welfare protections, social vulnerability remains significant. Children and adolescents are more exposed to poverty and social exclusion than the general population, and material deprivation continues to affect a non-negligible share of young households.

Structural barriers also persist in access to housing, employment, and education, especially for care leavers, migrant youth, and early school leavers. In the labour market, young people without Austrian citizenship face substantially higher unemployment risks, while disadvantaged family backgrounds and low educational attainment continue to constrain opportunities.

3 Insights from the interview: policy proponent

To inform the analysis, an interview was conducted with a policy maker³ who as member of the Green Party and who was directly involved in the policy creation and implementation. While this provides a direct insight to the policy construction and development, it is limited to a one-sided perspective that could be expanded by provided further alternative opinion on the drivers and challenges to this policy.

According to the interviewee, Austria has strong parties but relatively weak Parliament with strong party discipline that makes voting against the party line rare. The following leads to real decision-making processes happening in the government and party leadership, and not necessarily in the parliamentary debate. Thus, this somewhat limits the impact of engagement of the members of the parliament (MEPs) and civil society on the final decision.

According to the interviewee, the core drivers for the adoption of the reform were economists and climate scientists who were eager to “put a real cost on carbon” to manage the transition. As part of a larger tax package, the Eco Social Tax Reform aimed to increase the carbon price, lower labour taxes, lower corporate tax rates, and introduce the Klimabonus (subsequently weakened).

3.1 Policy Construction

The Greens were initially eager to include multiple MEPs and the coalition partners (conservatives) were not in favour. The only external stakeholders were experts that had been directly chosen as advisors to provide advice on the technical part of the carbon tax design. Based on the interviewee’s experience, the consultants and academics who understood the science needed for the reform as well as political processes and power dynamics were hence part of the discussion and were able to influence the framing of the policy reform.

“There were no citizens’ assembly and negotiations were carried out in small teams.”

3.2 Policy Design

The main idea of the policy was to integrate at national level the EU ETS with the assumption that carbon tax would render fossil fuels more expensive, leading to more sustainable choices undertaken to avoid expenses. In the case of the Klimabonus that was not implemented, revenue would be redistributed as lump-sum payments adjusted by region to incentivise low-carbon behaviour. The **Klimabonus** (“more for poor, less for rich” regressive concept) was not implemented, according to the interviewee, due to four main reasons: 1) data and timing; 2) household versus individual issue; 3) administrative complexity; 4) communication and

³ The name of the person interviewed was anonymised for confidentiality purposes.

perception challenges. The interviewee explains that throughout the policy implementation process, various parties did not think that Klimabonus would be useful.

As they proceed to further explain, in the first case (point 1), delays in data collection and monitoring, relative to what the reform envisaged, may generate allocation inefficiencies. Specifically, compensation mechanisms such as the Klimabonus risk being misdirected, for instance by overcompensating individuals who appear temporarily low-income despite having substantial underlying wealth and undercompensating genuinely vulnerable groups.

A related issue emerges in the second case (point 2): while taxation and administrative data are structured at the individual level, economic vulnerability is inherently a household-level phenomenon. This mismatch may produce distortions in distributional outcomes. For example, it may fail to adequately distinguish between individuals with low reported income but high household resources (i.e. minors in wealthy households) and those with relatively higher individual income but greater economic responsibility (i.e. single mothers).

All the above would have to be tackled by diverse offices, since the Klimabonus would have to be paid out by the Ministry of Climate Action and Energy, yet income data is collected by the Ministry of Finance Affairs. Therefore, this would require combination and bureaucratic reviews of their own governmental procedures.

Finally, according to the interviewee taxing bonuses was attacked, "...by populists" (this refers to the opposing parties, see Table 1). In addition, in parallel the Government was implementing budget cuts, which led to taking this compensation mechanism out of the reform. Distributional analysis performed for the reform suggested that, while the carbon tax is inherently regressive, the inclusion of the Klimabonus appears to have rendered the overall policy package progressive.

"I expect extreme backlash when the rest of Europe will require compensation measures, similar to the yellow vests (gilets jaunes) observed in France, since it is easier for the populists to blame Europe and its climate policies"

When it comes to public receipt of the entire Eco-Soc Tax reform, the public did not react positively observing higher prices for certain products (i.e. car fuel) and having not made the link between the reform and the Klimabonus. After the bonus was removed from the reform it was replaced by the commuter subsidy.

The policymaker explained that the commuter subsidy was simply a way to avoid abolishing the whole reform that seemed to be unfair after the Klimabonus removal. The example they provided concerns the renters living outside main urban centres who pay the carbon tax but receive no compensation. This means that if households (including poorer) have to pay a higher share of income on energy without compensation, the tax is unfair. The latter

reasoning seems to showcase the willingness on the policymakers' side to provide a more balanced policy. It is acknowledged that policy development and implementation is not only time consuming but also expensive, therefore, what this interviewee seems to suggest is that overall, parties were willing to propose a viable policy option instead of Klimabonus rather than erasing entirely the “fairness” logic it was grounded in at policy design stage.

3.3 Policy Implementation

In retrospect, the interviewed policymaker believes it would have been beneficial to carry out more public campaigns before reform implementation, ensure the reform is submitted for discussion by citizens' assemblies, and construct an overall stronger public understanding of the rationale of the reform. This includes making clear linkages between the carbon pricing and Klimabonus in consultation process and promotional campaigns for the reform. Among the points that marked the reform design was the tension between power-strategic secrecy that marks Austrian decision-making process and democratic inclusion expected for this type of decisions. That tension ended up hurting the perceived fairness of the reform by the public and parties, reducing the social acceptability of the Klimabonus within the Eco Social Reform Tax. Drawing on this learning, it seems like a clear communication and citizen inclusion through for citizens' assemblies could have helped ensure the public acceptance of the reform and its subsequent implementation.

4 Policy Analysis

For the analysis, it would be important to take into consideration two elements that concern the economic performance and existing inequalities, as well as the overall climate policy framework and perception.

According to Eder et al., (2023) [R9], since the 1990s Austria has undergone notable economic and social changes which affected various aspects of life, such as labour access. While social security has remained quite robust, the economic crises in 2000s and 2008-2009 [R10] have affected the increase of low-wage employment [R11]. Other secondary yet relevant issue concerns scholarly social permeability, where children from the working-class families still have a lower probability of completing high school [R12]. In addition, it appears that education does not currently pay off as it used to for past generations as higher education is no longer reflected in higher salaries which raises institutional barriers for employment in the context of the increased immigration [R13⁴]. Furthermore, in the Austrian case, the gender disparity remained an issue in 2020, as the country noted a larger difference in working women and their wages compared to their male counterparts [R14] [R15]. To address the regressive effects of tax increases, the government introduced compensatory programmes aimed at reducing resulting these type of inequalities [R16].

Regarding the Austrian's commitments to climate action, the country is not on track to reach its Paris Agreement (Figure 5), based on data collected by the OECD (2019) [R17].

Per capita metric tons of CO₂ equivalent

Figure 5. Country emissions and commitment to climate action measured per capita metric tons of CO₂ (1990 – 2030); Source: World Population Prospects 2019 [R18]⁵

⁴ This unit is measured via Gini coefficient looking at measuring inequality.

⁵ Note: Total GHG emissions exclude LULUCF (land-use, land-use change and forestry). Scatters in 2030 indicate IMF implied unconditional nationally determined contribution (NDC) economy-wide target levels on GHGs excluding LULUCF. The population estimate for 2030 is based on the UN population data with the

In the interview, the policymaker framed the policy as a mechanism to tax polluters while redistributing the revenues through compensation payments, with the explicit objective of offsetting social inequalities.

Mayer et al (2021) show that carbon pricing in Austria can accelerate the adoption of climate-neutral technologies, while in some sectors alternative demand-side instruments may be more effective. The research acknowledges that the mechanism should account for the public-good benefits generated by carbon pricing at the household level, moving beyond the assumption of equal per-capita allocation. Mayer et al. (2021) suggest that future research should focus on the public budget and welfare implications, and the weakening of the Klimabonus with the barriers of the Eco Soc Tax Reform, demonstrate the reality of their statement where efforts to bring improvements via climate policies are diminished if social welfare pays the cost.

As the table outlines (Table 3), there are several drivers that address power distribution leading to inequality imbalances. Although these same imbalances are not meant to undermine the issue of inequality, the perception (regardless of its correctness) of the same can lead to a problem.

Table 3 Policy Drivers

Subcategory	Definition	Example
Societal Challenges		
Social Inequality and Vulnerability	Gaps in income, energy poverty, exposure to risk	Poorer households hit harder by carbon tax without compensation
Education and Skills	Social demand for skills needed in transition	Citizens need to understand (and be included) carbon pricing to support reforms
Economic Dynamics		
Fiscal Constraints	Need to balance budgets, tax trade-offs	Government kept the carbon tax because needed the revenue
Market Structure	Urban–rural differences, type of economy	Higher car dependence in rural Austria influences acceptance
Legal Landscape		

medium-variant projection. Dotted lines refer to the linear emission trajectories required to reach the announced targets in 2030.

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New Regulations	Legislative changes impacting policy	ETS2 incoming need compensation tools
Administrative Requirements	Legal feasibility & process	Klimabonus should have had to run through separate ministries can lead to complexity
International Relations		
EU Policy Pressures	External obligations	ETS2 will impose carbon pricing weighting on the national compensation that will be needed
Geopolitical & Energy Security	External shocks impacting policy	Energy crisis after Russia–Ukraine war influenced fuel prices and acceptance

The main drivers of the policy are economic instability balanced with endogenous and exogenous pressures to provide a fair carbon market to reduce emissions. This policy analysis provides mainly data from external sources and single interview highlighting the persisting challenges to comply to the EU (environmental) pressures. If the main aim is to reduce costs (i.e. energy) due to geopolitical shocks, the indirect effect is balancing it with national circumstances. The relationship between policy factors are presented in the next section with a theory of change diagram.

Considering the quite diverse set of policy drivers (Table 1), it appears clear that the Eco Soc Tax is necessary to address the inequality resulting from efforts to reduce emissions. However, as the interview and data preliminarily presented suggest, if implemented incorrectly the potential of the policy results are weaker than expected. Furthermore, the integration of the policy with the ETS will be postponed to 2028 and is currently being implemented under the national carbon tax regulation [R40].

Figure 6. Summary table on Austria's green transition

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101132559.

5 Conclusion

Austria's 2022 Eco-Social Tax reform shows that the equity outcomes of carbon pricing depend at least as much on governance, compensation design, and implementation capacity as on the CO₂ price itself. In Austria, the reform emerged from coalition dynamics within a highly centralised decision-making setting, with limited scope for broad stakeholder involvement with a small set of experts selected. Together these factors narrowed political ownership and constrained deliberation on distributional trade-offs.

While the reform initially paired the CO₂ levy with the Klimabonus to safeguard social acceptability, the compensatory logic did not translate clearly "on the ground": citizens struggled to connect higher prices to the rebate, especially during the 2022–2023 energy crisis. Subsequent political change and fiscal pressures culminated in the abolition of the Klimabonus while maintaining the CO₂ price, effectively removing the main balancing mechanism and making the policy profile more regressive, placing higher burden on poorer households. Even if the commuter subsidy was introduced further to compensate for the social equity element, it seemed to ineffectively offset the negative social effects of the carbon tax. Households reliant on gas heating and those outside main centres who face limited alternatives have been even more concerned by the negative effects of the reform.

The main elements that could contribute to better policy delivery are: 1) coherence in proposed policy mechanism that relies on broad consensus from the political parties and engagement of citizens; 2) efficient communication on the rationale and objectives of the policy accompanied by dedicated consultation and awareness-raising activities for the population. Governmental support contributed to initial policy design of Eco-Social Tax with inequalities in mind which was translated in Klimabonus. However, further dissensions and outside shocks did not allow for its implementation. Overall, it is worth noting the weight of the political system on policy design and implementation.

The inequality was not only produced by "the tax" but by implementation constraints and perceived (un)fairness. The analysis points to practical barriers that undermined a more targeted, progressive compensation, namely data lags, the mismatch between individual tax data and household poverty, gaps in cross-ministry coordination, and communication challenges. In parallel, the public often failed to connect higher prices to the bonus fuelling perceptions of unfairness and weakening legitimacy of the reform, which in turn led to actual unequal policy practice.

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